

STUDY OF A FOUR-DIMENSIONAL TRANSPORTATION PROBLEM

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Abstract

Purpose – Solving and analyzing a four-dimensional Transportation Problem is the purpose of this paper.

Methodology/approach – The theoretical study of the paper contains the development of the mathematical model of the studied problem and a proposed methodology for solving and analyzing it. A numerical case study is treated based on the methodology to demonstrate its applicability.

Findings – The mathematical model and the methodology for solving and analyzing a four-dimensional Transportation Problem are proposed. The sensitivity analysis of the solution, the parametric analyze of some coefficients, the solving of the problem in cases of additional imposed constraints are also possible.

Research limitations/implications – The proposed methodology is applicable to a variety of cases of a four-dimensional Transportation Problem.

Practical implications – The paper offers the practical possibility to treat a class of real four-index Transportation Problem, for which the methods of solving the classical two-index Transportation Problem are not applicable. It can also performs sensitivity and parametric analyzes, as well as the solving, by means of software WinQSB.

Originality/value – The proposed method represents a very useful tool for managers to ensure an efficient leading for transporting heterogeneous commodities with the lowest possible cost involved.

Key words: Transportation Problem, optimal solution, WinQSB.

Introduction

Over the past two decades, the globalization has defined the business landscape by growing cross-border interconnectedness, reflected in the global flows of people, capital, products, services, knowledge, information, technologies and culture. New communication technologies correlated with the decreasing transportation costs increase the opportunity to connect with anyone from anywhere and to discover new business opportunities.

This paper addresses the issue of transport of goods and services across the global marketplace, an indispensable economic factor, which contributes to the successful operation of management in the globalized economy. At the same time, this paper aims to emphasize the increasing need for global managers operating in business to respond effectively to the challenges of globalization and to provide responses and training for managers.

Transportation Problem is one of the most important applications of quantitative analysis due to its spreading in real life (Hillier and Lieberman, 2015). The classical Transportation Problem is a two-dimensional problem in which a single commodity (homogeneous product) is directly shipped from a set of source centers to a set of destination centers (Hitchcock, 1941). The sum of the amounts available at the sources is equal to the sum of the demands at the various destinations. The goal is to determine the amounts of the commodity to be transported over all routes so that the total transportation cost is minimized.

Many researchers have extensively studied such cost-time transportation problems: discussing variants of the Transportation Problem (Appa, 1973); transportation with mixed constraints (Brigden, 1974); a specialized method of the Transportation Problem with additional linear constraints (Klingman and Russel, 1975); the branching method for fixed-charge Transportation Problem (Adlakha et al., 2010); solving transportation problem with the various method of linear programming problem (Sharma et al., 2012).

When planning transportation, a situation occurs when the commodity is delivered to consumers not directly but through intermediate centers (warehouses, secondary processing enterprises, etc.), called a three-dimensional Transportation Problem with intermediate centers (Raskin et al., 2017).

Recently, the Transportation Problem with sources, destinations and various commodities, so another three-dimensional Transportation Problem, is treated by a few researches (Pudasaini and Shrestha, 2019).

In this paper, a four-dimensional Transportation Problem with source availabilities, destination demands, intermediate centers and several types of commodities is analyzed and solved. Subsequently, other additional constraints are added to the initial considered problem: the restricting access on certain transport routes; minimum shipping guarantees from certain specified routes. The approach of such situations is included in the numerical case studied in the paper.

Mathematical model of a four-dimensional Transportation Problem

In a four-dimensional Transportation Problem it is considered that several types of products, $P_l, l \in \overline{1, q}$, must be transported from the producer centers, $A_i, i \in \overline{1, m}$, for the consumer centers $B_j, j \in \overline{1, n}$. In addition, it is assumed that each type of product P_l will pass through one of the intermediate centers $D_k, k \in \overline{1, p}$, before reaching a consumer center.

Let us introduce the following notations for the known data of the considered problem:

a_i - the total quantity of products intended for transportation from the i -th production center, $a_i > 0, i \in \overline{1, m}$;

b_j - the demanded total quantity of products at j -th consumer center, $b_j > 0, j \in \overline{1, n}$;

d_k - the permissible total quantity of products transported through the k -th intermediate center, $d_k > 0, k \in \overline{1, p}$;

f_l - the transported enter quantity of the l -th product, $f_l > 0, l \in \overline{1, q}$;

c_{ijkl} - the transportation cost of one unit of the l -th product, from the i -th producer center, to the j -th consumer center, through the k -th intermediate center, $c_{ijkl} > 0$.

The objective of the problem is to determine the amounts shipped from each production center to each consumer center to minimize the total transportation cost.

Let x_{ijkl} ($i \in \overline{1, m}, j \in \overline{1, n}, k \in \overline{1, p}, l \in \overline{1, q}$) be the variables, i.e. the quantity of product P_l shipped from the center A_i to center B_j through the center D_k .

Using the notations introduced above and the linear programming approach, the mathematical model of this four-dimensional Transportation Problem can be formulated as follows:

$$\text{Minimize: } z = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^q c_{ijkl} x_{ijkl} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Subject to: } \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^q x_{ijkl} = a_i, \quad i \in \overline{1, m} \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^q x_{ijkl} = b_j, \quad j \in \overline{1, n} \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{l=1}^q x_{ijkl} = d_k, \quad k \in \overline{1, p} \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^p x_{ijkl} = f_l, \quad l \in \overline{1, q} \quad (5)$$

$$x_{ijkl} \geq 0, \quad i \in \overline{1, m}, \quad j \in \overline{1, n}, \quad k \in \overline{1, p}, \quad l \in \overline{1, q} \quad (6)$$

where: $a_i > 0, i \in \overline{1, m}; b_j > 0, j \in \overline{1, n}; d_k > 0, k \in \overline{1, p}; f_l > 0, l \in \overline{1, q}$.

The necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of a feasible solution to the above model is:

$$\sum_{i=1}^m a_i = \sum_{j=1}^n b_j = \sum_{k=1}^p d_k = \sum_{l=1}^q f_l \quad (7)$$

The objective function (1) is to minimize the total logistics cost for shipping all products. The constraints (2) define the supply restrictions at the producer centers. The constraints (3) define the demand restrictions at the consumer centers. The constraints (4) refer to the capacities of the intermediate centers, and the constraints (5) specify the quantity of each type of product.

The obtained four-index mathematical model contains a system of $m + n + p + q$ constraints of which $m + n + p + q - 3$ are independent, and $m \cdot n \cdot p \cdot q$ unknowns. In the model, both the objective function (1) and the constraints (2)-(5) have a linear relationship, so it is a linear programming model.

Particular cases of the above model are the following:

a) In this case, $c_{ijkl} > 0, a_i > 0, b_j > 0, d_k > 0, i \in \overline{1, m}, j \in \overline{1, n}, k \in \overline{1, p}, l \in \overline{1, q}$ are known.

The mathematical model contains only three categories of restrictions; it obtains:

$$\text{Minimize: } z = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^q c_{ijkl} x_{ijkl}$$

$$\text{Subject to: } \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^q x_{ijkl} = a_i, \quad i \in \overline{1, m}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^q x_{ijkl} = b_j, \quad j \in \overline{1, n}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{l=1}^q x_{ijkl} = d_k, \quad k \in \overline{1, p}$$

$$x_{ijkl} \geq 0, i \in \overline{1, m}, j \in \overline{1, n}, k \in \overline{1, p}, l \in \overline{1, q}$$

with the necessary and sufficient condition:

$$\sum_{i=1}^m a_i = \sum_{j=1}^n b_j = \sum_{k=1}^p d_k \quad (8)$$

There are $C_4^3 = 4$ variants.

b) In this case, $c_{ijkl} > 0, a_i > 0, b_j > 0, i \in \overline{1, m}, j \in \overline{1, n}, k \in \overline{1, p}, l \in \overline{1, q}$ are known.

The mathematical model contains only two categories of restrictions; it obtains:

$$\text{Minimize: } z = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^q c_{ijkl} x_{ijkl}$$

$$\text{Subject to: } \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^q x_{ijkl} = a_i, i \in \overline{1, m}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^q x_{ijkl} = b_j, j \in \overline{1, n}$$

$$x_{ijkl} \geq 0, i \in \overline{1, m}, j \in \overline{1, n}, k \in \overline{1, p}, l \in \overline{1, q}$$

with the necessary and sufficient condition:

$$\sum_{i=1}^m a_i = \sum_{j=1}^n b_j \quad (9)$$

There are $C_4^2 = 6$ variants.

Methodology for solving and analyzing a four-dimensional Transportation Problem

Due to the large number of variables and constraints, the mathematical model (1)-(6) is more complex than the two-index mathematical model of the typical Transportation Problem. For this reason, unlike the typical Transport Problem, only the simplex algorithm can be used to solve this studied model.

The proposed methodology for solving and analyzing a four-dimensional Transportation Problem includes the following steps:

1. Define the objective function to be minimized with the constraints imposed on the problem.
2. Testing the necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of a feasible solution to the problem.
3. Finding the optimal solution and the optimal value of the objective function.
4. Perform the sensitivity analysis of the solution and develop the economic interpretation of the results.
5. Perform the parametric analysis relative to some different coefficients of the model and develop the economic interpretation of the results.
6. Finding the optimal solution in case of restricting access on certain transport routes from the problem.

7. Finding the solution in case of imposing certain conditions regarding the quantities transported on some routes from the problem.

Therefore, the four-dimensional Transportation Problem, formalized by the mathematical model (1)-(6), represents a multi-product Transportation Problem with intermediate centers. If we keep the notations, except for $k \in \overline{1, p}$, with which we will denote different means of transport for which the cost of transporting a unit of product is different (i.e. the transportation cost for a unit of product and over the same distance, it is assumed that it depends so much on the nature of product and the type of used means of transport), then the optimal solution of the problem allows the determination of a transport plan with a minimum total cost.

Numerical case study

Consider the following four-dimensional Transportation Problem involving: two producer centers (A_1, A_2), three consumer centers (B_1, B_2, B_3), two intermediate centers (D_1, D_2), two products (P_1, P_2).

The known numerical data of the problem are the following (with the abbreviations: u. for units; m.u. for monetary units): $a_1 = 500$ u., $a_2 = 400$ u., $b_1 = 250$ u., $b_3 = 300$ u., $d_1 = 420$ u., $d_2 = 480$ u., $f_1 = 470$ u., $f_2 = 430$ u., $c_{1111} = 3$ m.u., $c_{1112} = 5$ m.u., $c_{1121} = 4,5$ m.u., $c_{1122} = 4$ m.u. , $c_{1211} = 3,5$ m.u. , $c_{1212} = 6$ m.u. , $c_{1221} = 5,5$ m.u. , $c_{1222} = 6,5$ m.u. , $c_{1311} = 6$ m.u. , $c_{1312} = 5$ m.u. , $c_{1321} = 5$ m.u. , $c_{1322} = 4$ m.u. , $c_{2111} = 4,5$ m.u. , $c_{2112} = 4$ m.u. , $c_{2121} = 3,5$ m.u. , $c_{2122} = 3$ m.u. , $c_{2211} = 7$ m.u. , $c_{2212} = 5$ m.u. , $c_{2221} = 7$ m.u. , $c_{2222} = 5,5$ m.u. , $c_{2311} = 4$ m.u. , $c_{2312} = 4,5$ m.u. , $c_{2321} = 6$ m.u. , $c_{2322} = 5$ m.u.

- a) Determining the optimum mode of transport to minimize the total cost of distributing the quantities of products.
- b) Performing the sensitivity analysis of the solution.
- c) Performing the parametric analysis relative to the unit transportation cost c_{2122} .
- d) Solving the problem in case of blocking the access on the route between the center A_2 and the center B_3 .
- e) Solving the problem provided that a total quantity of products greater than or equal to 210 u. is transported on the route between the center A_1 and the center D_2 .

The detailed literary mathematical model of this problem is:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Minimize : } z = & c_{1111}x_{1111} + c_{1112}x_{1112} + c_{1121}x_{1121} + c_{1122}x_{1122} + \\ & + c_{1211}x_{1211} + c_{1212}x_{1212} + c_{1221}x_{1221} + c_{1222}x_{1222} + \\ & + c_{1311}x_{1311} + c_{1312}x_{1312} + c_{1321}x_{1321} + c_{1322}x_{1322} + \\ & + c_{2111}x_{2111} + c_{2112}x_{2112} + c_{2121}x_{2121} + c_{2122}x_{2122} + \\ & + c_{2211}x_{2211} + c_{2212}x_{2212} + c_{2221}x_{2221} + c_{2222}x_{2222} + \\ & + c_{2311}x_{2311} + c_{2312}x_{2312} + c_{2321}x_{2321} + c_{2322}x_{2322} \end{aligned}$$

Subject to :

$$\begin{aligned}
& x_{1111} + x_{1112} + x_{1121} + x_{1122} + x_{1211} + x_{1212} + x_{1221} + x_{1222} + \\
& \quad + x_{1311} + x_{1312} + x_{1321} + x_{1322} = a_1 \\
& x_{2111} + x_{2112} + x_{2121} + x_{2122} + x_{2211} + x_{2212} + x_{2221} + x_{2222} + \\
& \quad + x_{2311} + x_{2312} + x_{2321} + x_{2322} = a_2 \\
& x_{1111} + x_{1112} + x_{1121} + x_{1122} + x_{2111} + x_{2112} + x_{2121} + x_{2122} = b_1 \\
& x_{1211} + x_{1212} + x_{1221} + x_{1222} + x_{2211} + x_{2212} + x_{2221} + x_{2222} = b_2 \\
& x_{1311} + x_{1312} + x_{1321} + x_{1322} + x_{2311} + x_{2312} + x_{2321} + x_{2322} = b_3 \\
& x_{1111} + x_{1112} + x_{1211} + x_{1212} + x_{1311} + x_{1312} + x_{2111} + x_{2112} + \\
& \quad + x_{2211} + x_{2212} + x_{2311} + x_{2312} = d_1 \\
& x_{1121} + x_{1122} + x_{1221} + x_{1222} + x_{1321} + x_{1322} + x_{2121} + x_{2122} + \\
& \quad + x_{2221} + x_{2222} + x_{2321} + x_{2322} = d_2 \\
& x_{1111} + x_{1121} + x_{1211} + x_{1221} + x_{1311} + x_{1321} + x_{2111} + x_{2121} + \\
& \quad + x_{2211} + x_{2221} + x_{2311} + x_{2321} = f_1 \\
& x_{1112} + x_{1122} + x_{1212} + x_{1222} + x_{1312} + x_{1322} + x_{2112} + x_{2122} + \\
& \quad + x_{2212} + x_{2222} + x_{2312} + x_{2322} = f_2 \\
& x_{ijkl} \geq 0, \quad i \in 1, 2, j \in 1, 3, k \in 1, 2, l \in 1, 2
\end{aligned}$$

It is a linear programming mathematical model with 24 variables nonnegative continuous and 9 constraints.

a) Because $\sum_{i=1}^2 a_i = \sum_{j=1}^3 b_j = \sum_{k=1}^2 d_k = \sum_{l=1}^2 f_l = 900 \text{ u.}$, the necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of a feasible solution is fulfilled.

Further, the problem is resolved using WinQSB software, the module *Linear and Integer Programming*, with the simplex algorithm.

The numerical data of the problem in matrix form, from the initial working window of the module, are presented in Fig.1.

Variable →	X1111	X1112	X1121	X1122	X1211	X1212	X1221	X1222	X1311	X1312	X1321	X1322
Minimize	3	5	4.5	4	3.5	6	5.5	6.5	6	5	5	4
C1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
C2												
C3	1	1	1	1								
C4					1	1	1	1				
C5									1	1	1	1
C6	1	1			1	1			1	1		
C7			1	1			1	1			1	1
C8	1		1				1		1		1	
C9		1		1		1		1		1		1
LowerBound	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
UpperBound	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M
VariableType	Continuous											

	X2111	X2112	X2121	X2122	X2211	X2212	X2221	X2222	X2311	X2312	X2321	X2322	Direction	R. H. S.
	4.5	4	3.5	3	7	5	7	5.5	4	4.5	6	5	=	500
	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	=	400
	1	1	1	1									=	250
					1	1	1	1					=	350
	1	1			1	1			1	1	1	1	=	300
			1	1			1	1					=	420
	1		1				1		1				=	480
	1	1		1		1		1		1			=	470
		1	1		1		1		1		1		=	430
	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M		
	Continuous													

Figure 1. The data of the initial problem in matrix form

With the command *Solve the Problem*, from the menu *Solve and Analyze*, the combined report is obtained in the results window (Fig.2,a). The optimal solution of the problem is displayed in the column *Solution Value* of the report. Table representation of this solution is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Table representation of the optimal solution from the Fig.2,a

		B_1	B_2	B_3
A_1	D_1	-	310 u. P_1	-
	D_2	-	-	190 u. P_2
A_2	D_1	-	-	110 u. P_1
	D_2	50 u. P_1 200 u. P_2	40 u. P_2	-

The minimum total cost of the transport corresponding to this solution is $z_{\min} = 3280$ m.u.

But the initial problem also admits a second optimal alternative solution. Its corresponding combined report is obtained with the command *Obtain Alternate Optimal* from the menu *Results* (Fig.2,b).

22:24:02		Wednesday		June	24	2020		
Decision Variable	Solution Value	Unit Cost or Profit c(j)	Total Contribution	Reduced Cost	Basis Status	Allowable Min. c(j)	Allowable Max. c(j)	
1	X1111	0	3.0000	0	2.0000	at bound	1.0000	M
2	X1112	0	5.0000	0	4.5000	at bound	0.5000	M
3	X1121	0	4.5000	0	2.0000	at bound	2.5000	M
4	X1122	0	4.0000	0	2.0000	at bound	2.0000	M
5	X1211	310.0000	3.5000	1.085.0000	0	basic	3.5000	4.5000
6	X1212	0	6.0000	0	3.0000	at bound	3.0000	M
7	X1221	0	5.5000	0	0.5000	at bound	5.0000	M
8	X1222	0	6.5000	0	2.0000	at bound	4.5000	M
9	X1311	0	6.0000	0	3.0000	at bound	3.0000	M
10	X1312	0	5.0000	0	2.5000	at bound	2.5000	M
11	X1321	0	5.0000	0	0.5000	at bound	4.5000	M
12	X1322	190.0000	4.0000	760.0000	0	basic	2.0000	4.0000
13	X2111	0	4.5000	0	2.5000	at bound	2.0000	M
14	X2112	0	4.0000	0	2.5000	at bound	1.5000	M
15	X2121	50.0000	3.5000	175.0000	0	basic	2.5000	4.0000
16	X2122	200.0000	3.0000	600.0000	0	basic	2.5000	4.0000
17	X2211	0	7.0000	0	2.5000	at bound	4.5000	M
18	X2212	0	5.0000	0	1.0000	at bound	4.0000	M
19	X2221	0	7.0000	0	1.0000	at bound	6.0000	M
20	X2222	40.0000	5.5000	220.0000	0	basic	4.5000	5.5000
21	X2311	110.0000	4.0000	440.0000	0	basic	3.0000	4.0000
22	X2312	0	4.5000	0	1.0000	at bound	3.5000	M
23	X2321	0	6.0000	0	0.5000	at bound	5.5000	M
24	X2322	0	5.0000	0	0	at bound	5.0000	M
Objective	Function	(Min.) =	3.280.0000	(Note: Alternate Solution Exists!!)				
Constraint	Left Hand Side	Direction	Right Hand Side	Slack or Surplus	Shadow Price	Allowable Min. RHS	Allowable Max. RHS	
1	C1	=	500.0000	0	-1.0000	500.0000	580.0000	
2	C2	=	400.0000	0	0	400.0000	M	
3	C3	=	250.0000	0	-2.5000	250.0000	290.0000	
4	C4	=	350.0000	0	0	350.0000	M	
5	C5	=	300.0000	0	-0.5000	300.0000	380.0000	
6	C6	=	420.0000	0	-1.5000	420.0000	470.0000	
7	C7	=	480.0000	0	0	480.0000	M	
8	C8	=	470.0000	0	6.0000	430.0000	470.0000	
9	C9	=	430.0000	0	5.5000	390.0000	430.0000	

a)

22:26:33		Wednesday		June	24	2020		
Decision Variable	Solution Value	Unit Cost or Profit c(j)	Total Contribution	Reduced Cost	Basis Status	Allowable Min. c(j)	Allowable Max. c(j)	
1	X1111	0	3.0000	0	2.0000	at bound	1.0000	M
2	X1112	0	5.0000	0	4.5000	at bound	0.5000	M
3	X1121	0	4.5000	0	2.0000	at bound	2.5000	M
4	X1122	0	4.0000	0	2.0000	at bound	2.0000	M
5	X1211	350.0000	3.5000	1.225.0000	0	basic	3.0000	3.5000
6	X1212	0	6.0000	0	3.0000	at bound	3.0000	M
7	X1221	0	5.5000	0	0.5000	at bound	5.0000	M
8	X1222	0	6.5000	0	2.0000	at bound	4.5000	M
9	X1311	0	6.0000	0	3.0000	at bound	3.0000	M
10	X1312	0	5.0000	0	2.5000	at bound	2.5000	M
11	X1321	0	5.0000	0	0.5000	at bound	4.5000	M
12	X1322	150.0000	4.0000	600.0000	0	basic	4.0000	4.5000
13	X2111	0	4.5000	0	2.5000	at bound	2.0000	M
14	X2112	0	4.0000	0	2.5000	at bound	1.5000	M
15	X2121	50.0000	3.5000	175.0000	0	basic	2.5000	4.0000
16	X2122	200.0000	3.0000	600.0000	0	basic	2.5000	4.0000
17	X2211	0	7.0000	0	2.5000	at bound	4.5000	M
18	X2212	0	5.0000	0	1.0000	at bound	4.0000	M
19	X2221	0	7.0000	0	1.0000	at bound	6.0000	M
20	X2222	0	5.5000	0	0	at bound	5.5000	M
21	X2311	70.0000	4.0000	280.0000	0	basic	4.0000	4.5000
22	X2312	0	4.5000	0	1.0000	at bound	3.5000	M
23	X2321	0	6.0000	0	0.5000	at bound	5.5000	M
24	X2322	80.0000	5.0000	400.0000	0	basic	4.5000	5.0000
Objective	Function	(Min.) =	3.280.0000	(Note: Alternate Solution Exists!!)				
Constraint	Left Hand Side	Direction	Right Hand Side	Slack or Surplus	Shadow Price	Allowable Min. RHS	Allowable Max. RHS	
1	C1	=	500.0000	0	-1.0000	500.0000	580.0000	
2	C2	=	400.0000	0	0	400.0000	M	
3	C3	=	250.0000	0	-2.5000	250.0000	290.0000	
4	C4	=	350.0000	0	0	350.0000	M	
5	C5	=	300.0000	0	-0.5000	300.0000	380.0000	
6	C6	=	420.0000	0	-1.5000	420.0000	470.0000	
7	C7	=	480.0000	0	0	480.0000	M	
8	C8	=	470.0000	0	6.0000	430.0000	470.0000	
9	C9	=	430.0000	0	5.5000	390.0000	430.0000	

b)

Figure 2. Combined reports of the initial problem

Table representation of this second optimal solution is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Table representation of the optimal solution from the Fig.2,b

		B_1	B_2	B_3
A_1	D_1	-	350 u. P_1	-
	D_2	-	-	150 u. P_2
A_2	D_1	-	-	70 u. P_1
	D_2	50 u. P_1 200 u. P_2	-	80 u. P_2

The existence of two basic optimal solutions shows that the initial problem admits the following general optimal solution:

$$x = (0, 0, 0, 0, 310\lambda_1 + 350\lambda_2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 190\lambda_1 + 150\lambda_2, 0, 0, 50, 200, 0, 0, 0, 40\lambda_1, 110\lambda_1 + 70\lambda_2, 0, 0, 80\lambda_2), \text{ with } \lambda_1, \lambda_2 \geq 0, \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 1.$$

Table representation of this general optimal solution is presented in Table 3 and a network representation is illustrated in Fig.3

Table 3. Table representation of the general optimal solution

		B_1	B_2	B_3
A_1	D_1	-	$310 \cdot \lambda_1 + 350 \cdot \lambda_2 \text{ u. } P_1$	-
	D_2	-	-	$190 \cdot \lambda_1 + 150 \cdot \lambda_2 \text{ u. } P_2$
A_2	D_1	-	-	$110 \cdot \lambda_1 + 70 \cdot \lambda_2 \text{ u. } P_1$
	D_2	$50 \text{ u. } P_1$ $200 \text{ u. } P_2$	$40 \cdot \lambda_1 \text{ u. } P_2$	$80 \cdot \lambda_2 \text{ u. } P_2$

Figure 3. A network representation of the general optimal solution

b) For a certain optimal solution of the problem, the columns *Allowable Min $c[i]$* and *Allowable Max $c[i]$* , from the corresponding combined report (see Fig.2), contain, for each variable x_{ijkl} , the extremities of an interval in which the coefficient c_{ijkl} can take values so that the optimal solution of the problem remains unchanged.

Thus for the solution from the combined report, presented in Fig.2,a, it obtains:

$$c_{1111} \in [1, \infty), c_{1112} \in [0,5; \infty), c_{1121} \in [2,5; \infty), c_{1122} \in [2, \infty), c_{1211} \in [3,5; 4,5] \text{ and so on.}$$

c) For the parametric analysis relative to the values of the unit transportation cost, respectively, to the corresponding coefficient from the objective function, the command *Perform Parametric Analysis*, from the menu *Solve and Analyze*, is called. It displays the dialog box *Parametric Analysis*, in which the selections shown in Fig.4 are performed. A click on the *OK* command button displays in the results window the table with the parametric analysis in relation to the unit cost c_{2122} (Fig.5).

Figure 4. The dialog box Parametric Analysis

Range	From Coeff. of X2122	To Coeff. of X2122	From OBJ Value	To OBJ Value	Slope	Leaving Variable	Entering Variable
1	3.0000	4.0000	3.280.0000	3.480.0000	200.0000	X2222	X2212
2	4.0000	4.0000	3.480.0000	3.480.0000	120.0000	X2311	X2312
3	4.0000	4.2500	3.480.0000	3.492.5000	50.0000	X2122	X2112
4	4.2500	M	3.492.5000	3.492.5000	0		
5	3.0000	2.5000	3.280.0000	3.180.0000	200.0000	X2121	X1221
6	2.5000	-M	3.180.0000	-M	250.0000		

Figure 5. Table with parametric analysis in relation to the unit cost c_{2122}

It is found that for $c_{2122} \geq 4,25$ m.u. the transport of product P_2 from A_2 to B_1 through D_2 is no longer performed. With the command *Graphic Parametric Analysis*, from the menu *Results*, it is obtained the graph of the variation of the total cost depending on the value of the parameter (Fig.6).

Figure 6. The graph of the parametric analysis in relation to the unit cost c_{2122}

d) The blocking of the access on the route between the centers A_2 and B_3 implies the disappearance of four variables (x_{2311} , x_{2312} , x_{2321} , x_{2322}) from the mathematical model of the problem. For this purpose, for each of these four variables, it can use the command *Delete a Variable* from the menu *Edit* in *WinQSB*, as in the Fig.7.

Figure 7. The dialog box *Delete a Variable*

In this case, two combined reports (Fig.8) are also obtained.

22:58:27		Thursday	June	25	2020		
Decision Variable	Solution Value	Unit Cost or Profit c(j)	Total Contribution	Reduced Cost	Basis Status	Allowable Min. c(j)	Allowable Max. c(j)
1	X1111	0	3.0000	0	1.0000	at bound	2.0000 M
2	X1112	0	5.0000	0	4.0000	at bound	1.0000 M
3	X1121	0	4.5000	0	3.5000	at bound	1.0000 M
4	X1122	0	4.0000	0	4.0000	at bound	0 M
5	X1211	200.0000	3.5000	700.0000	0	basic	-M 4.5000
6	X1212	0	6.0000	0	3.5000	at bound	2.5000 M
7	X1221	0	5.5000	0	3.0000	at bound	2.5000 M
8	X1222	0	6.5000	0	5.0000	at bound	1.5000 M
9	X1311	20.0000	6.0000	120.0000	0	basic	5.5000 6.0000
10	X1312	50.0000	5.0000	250.0000	0	basic	5.0000 5.0000
11	X1321	0	5.0000	0	0	at bound	5.0000 M
12	X1322	230.0000	4.0000	920.0000	0	basic	4.0000 4.0000
13	X2111	0	4.5000	0	0	at bound	4.5000 M
14	X2112	0	4.0000	0	0.5000	at bound	3.5000 M
15	X2121	250.0000	3.5000	875.0000	0	basic	-M 3.5000
16	X2122	0	3.0000	0	0.5000	at bound	2.5000 M
17	X2211	0	7.0000	0	1.0000	at bound	6.0000 M
18	X2212	150.0000	5.0000	750.0000	0	basic	4.0000 6.0000
19	X2221	0	7.0000	0	2.0000	at bound	5.0000 M
20	X2222	0	5.5000	0	1.5000	at bound	4.0000 M
Objective	Function	(Min.) =	3.615.0000	(Note: Alternate Solution Exists!!)			
Constraint	Left Hand Side	Direction	Right Hand Side	Slack or Surplus	Shadow Price	Allowable Min. RHS	Allowable Max. RHS
1	C1	=	500.0000	0	-2.5000	500.0000	520.0000
2	C2	=	400.0000	0	0	400.0000	M
3	C3	=	250.0000	0	-4.0000	250.0000	260.0000
4	C4	=	350.0000	0	-2.5000	350.0000	370.0000
5	C5	=	300.0000	0	0	300.0000	M
6	C6	=	420.0000	0	0	420.0000	M
7	C7	=	480.0000	0	-1.0000	480.0000	530.0000
8	C8	=	470.0000	0	8.5000	460.0000	470.0000
9	C9	=	430.0000	0	7.5000	410.0000	430.0000

a)

21:49:46		Thursday	June	25	2020		
Decision Variable	Solution Value	Unit Cost or Profit c(j)	Total Contribution	Reduced Cost	Basis Status	Allowable Min. c(j)	Allowable Max. c(j)
1	X1111	0	3.0000	0	1.0000	at bound	2.0000 M
2	X1112	0	5.0000	0	4.0000	at bound	1.0000 M
3	X1121	0	4.5000	0	3.5000	at bound	1.0000 M
4	X1122	0	4.0000	0	4.0000	at bound	0 M
5	X1211	200.0000	3.5000	700.0000	0	basic	-M 4.5000
6	X1212	0	6.0000	0	3.5000	at bound	2.5000 M
7	X1221	0	5.5000	0	3.0000	at bound	2.5000 M
8	X1222	0	6.5000	0	5.0000	at bound	1.5000 M
9	X1311	0	6.0000	0	0	at bound	6.0000 M
10	X1312	70.0000	5.0000	350.0000	0	basic	4.0000 5.0000
11	X1321	20.0000	5.0000	100.0000	0	basic	4.5000 5.0000
12	X1322	210.0000	4.0000	840.0000	0	basic	4.0000 4.5000
13	X2111	0	4.5000	0	0	at bound	4.5000 M
14	X2112	0	4.0000	0	0.5000	at bound	3.5000 M
15	X2121	250.0000	3.5000	875.0000	0	basic	-M 3.5000
16	X2122	0	3.0000	0	0.5000	at bound	2.5000 M
17	X2211	0	7.0000	0	1.0000	at bound	6.0000 M
18	X2212	150.0000	5.0000	750.0000	0	basic	4.0000 6.0000
19	X2221	0	7.0000	0	2.0000	at bound	5.0000 M
20	X2222	0	5.5000	0	1.5000	at bound	4.0000 M
Objective	Function	(Min.) =	3.615.0000	(Note: Alternate Solution Exists!!)			
Constraint	Left Hand Side	Direction	Right Hand Side	Slack or Surplus	Shadow Price	Allowable Min. RHS	Allowable Max. RHS
1	C1	=	500.0000	0	-2.5000	500.0000	520.0000
2	C2	=	400.0000	0	0	400.0000	M
3	C3	=	250.0000	0	-4.0000	250.0000	260.0000
4	C4	=	350.0000	0	-2.5000	350.0000	370.0000
5	C5	=	300.0000	0	0	300.0000	M
6	C6	=	420.0000	0	0	420.0000	M
7	C7	=	480.0000	0	-1.0000	480.0000	530.0000
8	C8	=	470.0000	0	8.5000	460.0000	470.0000
9	C9	=	430.0000	0	7.5000	410.0000	430.0000

b)

Figure 8. Combined reports of the problem in case of blocking access

Based on them, the general optimal solution of the problem in case of blocking access can be written:

$$x = (0, 0, 0, 0, 200, 0, 0, 0, 20\lambda_1, 50\lambda_1 + 70\lambda_2, 20\lambda_2, 230\lambda_1 + 210\lambda_2, 0, 0, 250, 0, 0, 150, 0, 0), \text{ with } \lambda_1, \lambda_2 \geq 0, \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 1.$$

The minimum total cost of the transport corresponding to this solution is $z_{\min} = 3615$ m.u.

Table representation of the above solution is presented in Table 4 and a network representation is illustrated in Fig.9.

Table 4. Table representation of the general optimal solution of the problem in case of blocking access

		B_1	B_2	B_3
A_1	D_1	-	$310 \cdot \lambda_1 + 350 \cdot \lambda_2$ u. P_1	-
	D_2	-	-	$190 \cdot \lambda_1 + 150 \cdot \lambda_2$ u. P_2
A_2	D_1	-	-	$110 \cdot \lambda_1 + 70 \cdot \lambda_2$ u. P_1
	D_2	50 u. P_1 200 u. P_2	$40 \cdot \lambda_1$ u. P_2	$80 \cdot \lambda_2$ u. P_2

Figure 9. A network representation of the general optimal solution of the problem in case of blocking access

e) Imposing the restriction as on the route between the center A_1 and the center D_2 , a total quantity of products greater than or equal to 210 u. to be transported, implies the addition of a new constraint, in the initial mathematical model of the problem, having the form:

$$x_{1121} + x_{1122} + x_{1221} + x_{1222} + x_{1321} + x_{1322} \geq 210$$

For this purpose it can use the command *Insert a Constraint* from *WinQSB* and it obtains the numerical model in matrix form, presented in Fig.10.

Variable →	X1111	X1112	X1121	X1122	X1211	X1212	X1221	X1222	X1311	X1312	X1321	X1322
Minimize	3	5	4.5	4	3.5	6	5.5	6.5	6	5	5	4
C1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
C2												
C3	1	1	1	1								
C4					1	1	1	1				
C5									1	1	1	1
C6	1	1			1	1			1	1		
C7			1	1			1	1			1	1
C8	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1
C9		1		1		1		1		1		1
C10			1	1			1	1			1	1
LowerBound	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
UpperBound	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M
VariableType	Continuous											

X2111	X2112	X2121	X2122	X2211	X2212	X2221	X2222	X2311	X2312	X2321	X2322	X2322	Direction	R. H. S.
4.5	4	3.5	3	7	5	7	5.5	4	4.5	6	5	5	=	500
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	=	400
1	1	1	1										=	250
				1	1	1	1						=	350
								1	1	1	1	1	=	300
1	1			1	1			1	1				=	420
		1	1			1	1			1	1	1	=	480
1		1		1		1		1		1			=	470
	1		1		1		1			1	1	1	=	430
													>=	210
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M		

Figure 10. The data of the problem in matrix form

The obtained combined report (Fig.11) indicates a unique optimal solution:

$$x = (0, 0, 0, 0, 290, 0, 40, 0, 0, 0, 0, 170, 0, 0, 10, 240, 0, 0, 0, 20, 130, 0, 0, 0)$$

23:06:09		Thursday	June	25	2020			
	Decision Variable	Solution Value	Unit Cost or Profit c(j)	Total Contribution	Reduced Cost	Basis Status	Allowable Min. c(j)	Allowable Max. c(j)
1	X1111	0	3.0000	0	2.0000	at bound	1.0000	M
2	X1112	0	5.0000	0	4.5000	at bound	0.5000	M
3	X1121	0	4.5000	0	1.5000	at bound	3.0000	M
4	X1122	0	4.0000	0	1.5000	at bound	2.5000	M
5	X1211	290.0000	3.5000	1.015.0000	0	basic	-M	4.5000
6	X1212	0	6.0000	0	3.0000	at bound	3.0000	M
7	X1221	40.0000	5.5000	220.0000	0	basic	5.0000	6.0000
8	X1222	0	6.5000	0	1.5000	at bound	5.0000	M
9	X1311	0	6.0000	0	3.5000	at bound	2.5000	M
10	X1312	0	5.0000	0	3.0000	at bound	2.0000	M
11	X1321	0	5.0000	0	0.5000	at bound	4.5000	M
12	X1322	170.0000	4.0000	680.0000	0	basic	3.5000	4.5000
13	X2111	0	4.5000	0	2.0000	at bound	2.5000	M
14	X2112	0	4.0000	0	2.0000	at bound	2.0000	M
15	X2121	10.0000	3.5000	35.0000	0	basic	3.2500	4.0000
16	X2122	240.0000	3.0000	720.0000	0	basic	2.5000	3.2500
17	X2211	0	7.0000	0	2.0000	at bound	5.0000	M
18	X2212	0	5.0000	0	0.5000	at bound	4.5000	M
19	X2221	0	7.0000	0	1.0000	at bound	6.0000	M
20	X2222	20.0000	5.5000	110.0000	0	basic	4.5000	6.0000
21	X2311	130.0000	4.0000	520.0000	0	basic	3.0000	4.5000
22	X2312	0	4.5000	0	1.0000	at bound	3.5000	M
23	X2321	0	6.0000	0	1.0000	at bound	5.0000	M
24	X2322	0	5.0000	0	0.5000	at bound	4.5000	M
	Objective	Function	(Min.) =	3.300.0000				
	Constraint	Left Hand Side	Direction	Right Hand Side	Slack or Surplus	Shadow Price	Allowable Min. RHS	Allowable Max. RHS
1	C1	500.0000	=	500.0000	0	-1.5000	500.0000	540.0000
2	C2	400.0000	=	400.0000	0	0	400.0000	M
3	C3	250.0000	=	250.0000	0	-2.5000	250.0000	270.0000
4	C4	350.0000	=	350.0000	0	0	350.0000	M
5	C5	300.0000	=	300.0000	0	-1.0000	300.0000	340.0000
6	C6	420.0000	=	420.0000	0	-1.0000	420.0000	425.0000
7	C7	480.0000	=	480.0000	0	0	480.0000	M
8	C8	470.0000	=	470.0000	0	6.0000	460.0000	470.0000
9	C9	430.0000	=	430.0000	0	5.5000	410.0000	430.0000
10	C10	210.0000	>=	210.0000	0	1.0000	190.0000	215.0000

Figure 11. Combined reports of the initial problem

The minimum total cost of the transport corresponding to this solution is $z_{\min} = 3300$ m.u.

Table representation of this solution is presented in Table 5 and a network representation is illustrated in Fig.12.

Table 5. Table representation of the optimal solution from the Fig.11

		B_1	B_2	B_3
A_1	D_1	-	290 u. P_1	-
	D_2	-	40 u. P_1	170 u. P_2
A_2	D_1	-	-	130 u. P_1
	D_2	10 u. P_1 240 u. P_2	20 u. P_2	-

Figure 12. A network representation of the optimal solution from the Fig.11

Discussion and conclusions

Most of the models formulated for transportation problems have concentrated on shipping a single product or commodity to optimize the distribution network. Cases arise when multiple products have to be transported along similar routes.

This paper aims to be a guide to understand mathematical formalization, resolving and analyze of a four-dimensional Transportation Problem. The extension to four dimensions of the Transportation Problem is very important in the practice of the real-world, where the heterogeneous commodities shipping and more than two categories of centers involve a very large number of variables and constraints.

In the paper it is elaborated the mathematical model of the studied problem; it is formulated the necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of a feasible solution; it is proposed a methodology for solving and analyzing this problem. Finally, a numerical case study is treated in detail, based on the methodology, to demonstrate its applicability to a variety of cases.

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